

Applications of Omics analysis in supporting Toxicology and Safety Assessment Investigations

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Abstract

Modern toxicology is challenged in its aspiration to test and risk-assess the myriad of chemicals humans potentially can be exposed to. We still lack sufficient data to perform proper human risk assessments for a large proportion of environmental chemicals and we still know very little about many of the molecular mechanisms that cause adverse effects. In turn, lack of mechanistic insight delays the development of more cost-efficient and high-throughput alternative assays, which is a prerequisite if we are to deal with many untested compounds. One way to help speed up the effort is to take advantage of the many advances in omics technologies and apply them to toxicity testing strategies, or at the very least use them to better characterize the causative molecular mechanisms. Here, we discuss some of the applications of Omics technologies and how they can be applied to toxicology and safety assessment investigation.